

Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems

SYNERGIES

D1.2 Initial Data Management Plan

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The document provides guidelines and best practices for data management within the SYNERGIES project, ensuring its successful implementation. It is based on the Consortium Agreement (CA) and the Grant Agreement (GA). The CA contains the data management provisions agreed between the project partners. The GA contains the data management provisions agreed with the European Commission. These agreements are supplemented in the Data Management Plan (DMP) with project-level guidelines for processes and procedures to ensure effective data management.

Responsibility for the implementation of the DMP lies with all project members according to their roles and responsibilities. The Project Coordinator, Working Group Leaders and Task Leaders will ensure compliance with the DMP under the guidance and supervision of the Data Protection Officer.

Please note that the DMP in no way replaces the legal documents of the project and their application. In case of doubt, the legally binding documents take precedence.

The objective of this document is to outline the general data management plan for the project and the correct and appropriate handling of personal data that needs to be protected or that requires special treatment from an ethical point of view. When collecting, processing or using personal data by a project member, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other legal requirements must first be taken into account. These requirements are explained in the DMP.

In addition, the FAIR - Principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) are highlighted in the DMP as an important guideline to ensure findability, accessibility, interoperability and reproducibility of data. The principles are summarized in the DMP, together with an explanation of the commitment to follow these principles. The SYNERGIES project intends to follow the FAIR principles wherever possible, taking into account commercial and practical constraints.

The way in which the data is managed and disseminated is critical to the success of the project. The project unites a variety of partners with different internal processes and objectives from different sectors such as business, technology and research. It is essential to establish and maintain a common understanding of how data will be handled, the conditions under which data will be published and the procedures for agreeing these conditions. In this way, a culture of trust can be built that improves collaboration between partners and, ultimately, project outcomes. The DMP provides guidelines and recommendations for good practice that can be considered by partners in their daily interactions and in the appropriate application of due diligence.

As soon as the project partners recognize the relevance of the data and results for the public, they will evaluate the possibilities of publication in accordance with the guidelines of this DMP and the requirements of the CA and GA. The DMP contains best practices and procedures for the provision of data within the project and for the archiving and availability of these data beyond the project period.

This document provides initial guidance that explains project implementation in a simple and practical way, supports compliance with the underlying legal obligations and promotes the application of best data management practices.

As the project progresses, the DMP will be continuously updated to enable efficient integration, creation and management of FAIR data.

2 INTRODUCTION

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is an essential part of the work package (WP) WP1 "Project Coordination and Technical Management" in the SYNERGIES project. WP1 ensures that the project is carried out successfully. Professional management and efficient coordination make sure that the project objectives are achieved. WP1 is responsible for the entire technical and administrative project management and deals with all issues relating to data management and innovation management.

For successful project realisation, guidelines for the handling of research data must be established for the entire duration of the project and beyond. These guidelines are developed and recorded in the data management plan. The DMP serves as an orientation framework for how the project data is collected, organised, stored and used efficiently by defining the methodologies and standards to be adhered to, including determining the scope of data collection, processing and generation. This document also specifies whether and how the data will be shared or made openly accessible, taking into account personal data protection. In addition, plans are also drawn up for data handling, data curation and long-term preservation of the data (after the project).

All procedures and guidelines for the entire data cycle (Data Generation, Data Storage, Data Processing, Data Sharing, Data Retention and Archiving, Data Deletion or Disposal) within a project are described and provisionally defined in the DMP (Deliverable D1.2). This information is updated regularly in the mid-term DMP (Deliverable D1.3) and the final DMP (Deliverable 1.4).

The aim of this DMP is to ensure the correct handling of project data to comply with both the legal framework and regulations (e.g. protection of personal data) and the practices of Open Science. In the context of the DMP, this refers to open data, which is explained in greater detail in chapter 9.1. The open science practices will be done in conjunction with Task 10.2 (Dissemination).

A data management plan is an important tool that fulfils the following functions, among others:

- **Creating Consistency:** data may be handled at all stages by multiple users and in multiple systems. To ensure that data is easy to handle and fit for purpose, a DMP should establish rules which create consistency across all project data.
- **Ensuring Data Quality:** By defining data collection methods, validation techniques and quality assurance processes, a data management plan helps to ensure the accuracy, consistency and reliability of project data.
- **Mitigating Risks:** A data management plan identifies potential risks such as data loss, security breaches or non-compliance with regulations. It establishes safeguards to mitigate these risks and ensure data integrity and data privacy.
- **Facilitating Reproducibility:** Transparent and well-documented data management practices allow project results to be reproduced, validated and utilized by other members of the scientific community, thereby promoting scientific progress and innovation.

2.1 Structure of the deliverable D1.2

The document of the data management plan is divided into the following chapters:

The introduction explains what a data management plan is, how it is structured and what it is used for.

Chapter 3 presents the SYNERGIES project and the objectives to be achieved during the project. The work packages and project partners are also introduced here.

Chapter 4 describes the most important positions and responsibilities of the project in relation to the data.

Chapter 5 describes the data used in the project. This includes where the data comes from, the format in which it is stored, the size of the data and how it can be classified.

Chapter 6 delves into data management, detailing the naming conventions for data and the organization of the folder structure. It also outlines the procedures for version control. Additionally, this chapter lists the methods and software programmes necessary for data generation, presentation and processing.

Chapter 7 deals with data storage, both during and after the project. It details the locations, methods and amount of storage space needed throughout the project's duration. Additionally, it specifies the storage requirements for data archiving post-project, including the necessary storage space and the individuals responsible for managing this process.

Chapter 8 deals with data exchange both within the organisation and with external partners. This includes the definition of the data to be exchanged, the partners involved, the time and manner of data transfer. Compliance with the FAIR guidelines must be ensured, with the criteria of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of the data as well as public access to scientific data taking centre stage. This chapter also discusses which metadata standard is used in this project. In addition, the methods and software components required for data access and utilisation are described.

Chapter 9 explains the data restrictions. First, the basic principles for working with data in the context of open data are described. The principles of lawfulness, fairness, transparency, data minimisation, accuracy, storage limitation, etc. apply. In addition, the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which contains the guidelines for personal data, must be considered. In addition, there may be restrictions due to ethical aspects, which are discussed here.

Chapter 10 focuses on data security, detailing methods for secure data storage. Key aspects include data recovery, data backup and the transfer of sensitive data. The chapter also covers crucial elements such as confidentiality, communication security, data integrity and availability. Additionally, it outlines the procedures for data backup, specifying the number of independent storage locations required, the frequency of backups and the methods for testing the backup system.

Chapter 11 describes how and when the data and results are published, and which licences are used for this.

The penultimate chapter records the costs for data management, while the final chapter summarises the data management plan.

2.2 Partner consultations

In order to gain a better understanding of the data used and required in the project, a questionnaire was sent to the SYNERGIES members. This questionnaire (asked) inquired about their data needs, data processing requirements and data management requirements (see

attached questionnaire in the appendix A). This questionnaire will be sent to the SYNERGIES members at regular intervals to document changes in the data.

3 SYNERGIES - PROJECT SUMMARY

3.1 Introduction to the project

The SYNERGIES project (Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM (cooperative, connected and automated mobility) systems) is a European project funded by the EU research and innovation programme "Horizon Europe". SYNERGIES is represented by a consortium of 32 partners from 11 European countries, including leading vehicle manufacturers, suppliers, test laboratories and researchers.

The main objective of the SYNERGIES project is to develop a European scenario platform. This platform should fully enable the development, training, virtual testing and scalable scenario-based validation of CCAM systems. To this end, the Safety Assurance Framework developed in SUNRISE will be further developed in the following points:

- Expansion of the range of relevant scenarios through new scenarios for rural and urban environments that enable the descriptions of complex situations.
- Development of (semi)automatic AI (Artificial Intelligence) data processing tools for the extraction of scenarios.
- Provision of uniform access to a European Scenario Dataspace.
- Establishment of a marketplace to facilitate access to the tools for creating future scenarios.

In order to achieve this goal, five objectives were defined, which are described in more detail below.

3.2 Objectives

- **Objective 1: Deliver widely accessible scenarios.** Provision of scenarios for all stakeholders in the value chain through a scenario data space. Scaling up the SUNRISE framework by merging existing and newly developed scenario databases. The approach of this data space is to enable the provision of scenarios from day one by utilising existing initiatives and extending them with new initiatives. The aim is to build a dynamic EU-wide database that ensures efficient and up-to-date provision of relevant test scenarios.
- **Objective 2: Maximise the usability and coverage of the scenarios.** Maximise the usability and coverage of the scenarios to ensure the implementation of scenario-based validation. To achieve this, the requirements defined at the start of the project will consider a user-centred approach so that the SYNERGIES platform is specifically designed to satisfy the user needs of most relevant stakeholders. Additionally, SYNERGIES will enable the provision of scenario metadata that will allow a better understanding of the source, representativeness and limitations of the scenarios provided. AI tools will be developed and integrated into the toolchain to automatically obtain scenarios. The aim is to improve validation of CCAM systems through real and synthetic test scenarios covering as many traffic situations as possible that CCAM systems may face on European roads.
- **Objective 3: Enable the use of heterogeneous and inclusive data sources for the generation of scenarios.** This is to be achieved by evaluating and utilising different data sources. The following data sources can be considered: accident data, vehicle data,

infrastructure data, drone data. SYNERGIES will identify the most relevant data to be collected to obtain the scenarios required for the ODD (operational domain design) extension. The SYNERGIES platform includes a marketplace that provides all the tools needed to extract scenarios from raw data (and intermediate steps) to maximise the use of multiple sources. The objective is to employ the most suitable methods for capturing relevant traffic data, which will serve as a foundation for developing test scenarios across various traffic environments in line with the extended ODDs.

- **Objective 4: Achieve acceptance and upscaling of the proposed solution** through a transparent, holistic approach that is interoperable with the main previous EU projects (HEADSTART, SUNRISE, L3Pilot, Hi-Drive) and existing scenario database initiatives. The SYNERGIES platform will build on the outcome of the SUNRISE project, which relies on an international network of experts. In addition, the SYNERGIES platform will start with access to a large amount of data recorded on European roads. To maximise the scaling potential of the SYNERGIES platform, the project will develop and provide the necessary tools (via the marketplace) to integrate new initiatives and expand the platform.
- **Objective 5: Enable a solid AI foundation for CCAM** that includes the generation and enrichment of data (real and simulated) and scenarios to achieve improved data diversity, richness and completeness. Similarly, AI methods will complement the existing applications for identifying, extracting and generating scenarios and meet the requirements for ensuring safety and security. In addition, SYNERGIES will provide specific data sets for AI training and development. The dynamic scenario database will be used for AI development and training.

3.3 Work packages and deliverables

In order to successfully complete the SYNERGIES project and achieve the above-mentioned objectives, it is divided into ten work packages. The following section explains which tasks are dealt with in the individual work packages and Figure 1 shows the relationships between the various work packages.

Figure 1: SYNERGIES WPs and their main interactions

The following is a brief overview and description of the individual WPs:

- **WP1 - Coordination and management:** Ensures the successful execution of the project and its objectives.
- **WP2 - Requirements definition:** Defines user-centric requirements by compiling and analysing the needs of the stakeholders.

- **WP3 - Data analysis, collection, and generation:** Defines best practices for data collection, identifies suitable existing datasets and collects new data.
- **WP4 - Heterogeneous AI data processing tools and data interoperability:** Creates trustworthy AI data processing tools that span from raw data to metadata, ready for deployment in the SYNERGIES platform.
- **WP5 - Scenario generation methodology and process:** Develops the overall methodology to identify, extract, enrich, and generate scenarios.
- **WP6 - Governance sustainability and representativeness:** Defines how to govern the scenario platform with the continuous updates of data.
- **WP7 - SYNERGIES Platform establishment, testing and delivery:** Integrates, tests, and delivers the developed SYNERGIES platform and ensures its functionality, reliability, and usability for end users.
- **WP8 - Platform evaluation:** Develops an evaluation framework that will enable the assessment of the platform's performance, the fulfilment of user requirements, and the collection of feedback for continuous improvement.
- **WP9 - Stakeholder engagement:** Ensures the involvement stakeholder involvement for project result acceptance and uptake.
- **WP10 - Outreach:** Maximises the impact of the project through effective dissemination of the project results and communication with external entities.

3.4 Project partners

The SYNERGIES consortium comprises 32 project partners from eleven European countries (Figure 2). The participating project partners include leading vehicle manufacturers, suppliers, test laboratories and research institutes.

Figure 2: Countries of the SYNERGIES Project Partners

The participating project partners are listed below (Table 1).

Table 1: SYNERGIES Project partners

No.	Participant organisation name	Abbreviation	Country
1	IDIADA Automotive Technology, S.A.	IDI	ES
2	Bayerische Motoren Werke Aktiengesellschaft	BMW	DE
3	PSA Automobiles SA	PSA	FR
4	Renault SAS	REN	FR
5	Toyota Motor Europe NV	TME	BE
6	AVL List GmbH	AVL	AT
7	Centre Europeen d'études de securité et d'analyse des risques	CEESAR	FR
8	Association Europeenne Des Fournisseurs Automobiles	CLEPA	BE
9	Fundacion para la promocion de la innovacion investigacion y desarrollo tecnologico en la industria de automocion de Galicia	CTAG	ES
10	Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - und Raumfahrt EV	DLR	DE
11	European road transport telematics implementation coordination organisation - intelligent transport systems & services Europe	ERT	BE
12	Faurecia Clarion electronics Europe	FCE	FR
13	Erevnitiko panepistimiako institouto systimaton epikoinonion kai ypologiston	ICCS	GR
14	Rheinisch-Westfaelische Technische Hochschule Aachen	RWTH	DE
15	Institut de recherche technologique System X	IRTSX	FR
16	Ivex NV	IVEX	BE
17	Mosaic factor SL	MOSAIC	ES
18	Partners for automated vehicle education Europe	PAVE	BE
19	RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB	RISE	SE
20	SIEMENS industry software Netherlands BV	SIE-NL	NL
21	SIEMENS industry software NV	SIE-BE	BE

22	Nederlandse organisatie voor toegepast natuurwetenschappelijk onderzoek	TNO	NL
23	Technische Universiteit Eindhoven	TUE	NL
24	Universita degli studi di Genova	UNIGE	IT
25	The University of Warwick	UOW	UK
26	Fundacion centro de tecnologias de interaccion visual y comunicaciones	VICOM	ES
27	Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH	VIF	AT
28	Verkehrsunfallforschung an der TU Dresden GmbH	VUFO	DE
29	ZF Friedrichshafen AG	ZF	DE
30	* Torc Europe GmbH	TORC	DE
31	* Schweizerische Ruckversicherungs-Gesellschaft AG	SWRE	CH
32	* FEV IO GmbH	FEVIO	DE

4 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

It is recommended that the Consortium Agreement (CA) and Grant Agreement (GA) are consulted regarding data processing throughout the project. Additionally, key personnel involved in the project can offer valuable advice. Details about these key individuals are provided below.

- **Liaison and Collaboration Manager (LCM)**

The Liaison and Collaboration Manager supports and coordinates the collaboration between the project partners and external stakeholders (such as researchers, industry leaders and regulators) to guide the progress of the project. Continuous communication with key stakeholders will ensure that outcomes meet industry and regulatory expectations and maximize the impact of the project. By organizing workshops and collaboration platforms, feedback can be gathered and integrated into the project's development.

The role of Liaison and Collaboration Manager will be taken on by Iain Macbeth from ERTICO.

- **Dissemination Manager (DM)**

The Dissemination Manager (DM) of the project will be responsible for the dissemination and communication of the project results in cooperation with the project coordinator and the whole consortium throughout the project duration. Systematic dissemination of knowledge, research results and innovations will maximize the reach and impact of SYNERGIES and keep stakeholders informed about the progress of the project. Dissemination will be achieved through the publication of newsletters, reports, brochures, social media content and presentations. The DM will also plan and organize conferences, workshops and webinars. The DM will ensure that all EU directives and ethical guidelines are respected.

The role of Dissemination Manager will be taken on by Michael Karner from VIF.

- **Innovation and Exploitation Manager (IEM)**

The Innovation and Exploitation Manager (IEM) is responsible for ensuring the sustainable use of the project outcomes both during and after the project's completion. The IEM's role includes assessing the exploitation potential of identified innovations and developing strategies for their commercialization or utilization. In collaboration with the Steering Committee, the IEM develops and coordinates the necessary actions for the earliest possible market launch, taking into account the project objectives and legal framework conditions.

The role of Innovation and Exploitation Manager will be taken on by Stephane Dreher from ERTICO.

- **Data Protection Officer (DPO)**

The Data Protection Officer (DPO) ensures compliance with EU data protection laws, overseeing data privacy practices, conducting privacy impact assessments and advising on data protection obligations.

The DPO's tasks include advising the consortium on compliance with data protection laws. Another task is to support the implementation of data protection guidelines and practices. The DPO also provides management with guidelines on data protection risks. As an advisor, the DPO helps to understand and manage the data protection obligations without directly

managing the data protection procedures.

The role of Data Protection Officer will be taken on by Dorleta Garcia from VICOM.

- **Intellectual property rights Manager (IPRM)**

The Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Manager provides advisory and support services related to intellectual property within the consortium. This role includes assisting with the identification, management and protection of intellectual property rights arising from the consortium's activities. The IPR Manager advises on Intellectual Property (IP) strategy, facilitates the handling of IP issues among consortium members and ensures compliance with applicable laws and regulations, without directly managing the IP assets. The IPR Manager only acts if the parties request assistance.

The role of Intellectual property rights Manager will be taken on by Mariola Hauke from CLEPA.

5 DATA SCOPE AND DESCRIPTION

In SYNERGIES, within WP3, data from previous EU projects, accident databases and other initiatives will be analysed to check their quality and suitability for scenario creation. In addition, new data will be generated from a variety of sources including vehicles, mobile roadside units, drones, simulation tools and generative AI methods. These datasets will be used throughout the project to extract scenarios, which will be stored in the Scenario Platform for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems.

5.1 Data sources and formats

Below, initial information is provided for the different research outputs and produced data, reflecting the status. Different types of data and research outputs will be produced in SYNERGIES:

- Datasets collected from equipped vehicles e.g. radars, cameras, LiDARs (not yet defined).
- Datasets collected from mobile roadside units e.g. cameras, LiDARs (CSV-like data).
- Datasets collected from drones incl. camera data (CSV-like data).
- Datasets generated from advanced simulation tools and generative AI methods (CSV-like data).
- Scenario Platform, including relevant scenarios (not yet defined): openly available.
- Documentation of specifications and architecture (text, graphical): SYNERGIES public deliverables.
- Data from end-user questionnaires (text) -content and form carefully assessed and GDPR-compliant.

To effectively track changes and updates, it is highly advisable to create a comprehensive log of any updates or revisions made to the datasets. This log should meticulously document each change, including the date of the update, the nature of the revision, and the individual responsible for the modification. By maintaining such a detailed history of changes, we can ensure transparency and accountability throughout the data management process. This approach not only helps in keeping track of the evolution of the datasets but also facilitates easier troubleshooting and auditing, thereby enhancing the overall integrity and reliability of the data.

5.2 Data size (expected)

All data available in text or graphical form have very low size requirements (Kilobytes KBs/ Megabytes MBs). Concerning the datasets from vehicles, infrastructure, drones, simulation tools, which will be required for the verification of results and for reuse, the estimated size is in the order of Terabytes (TBs).

6 DATA HANDLING

Data handling is an important aspect that presents various complex challenges. These challenges arise mainly from the diversity of data types, the integration of real and synthetic data, the coexistence with iterative AI development and operation cycles and the associated storage and computational costs. To ensure trustworthy data processing, SYNERGIES is committed to the following principles:

- **Data Provenance Registry:** Every transaction is meticulously recorded to establish relationships that enable traceability of data transformations, conversions, transfers and more.
- **Data Management:** We emphasize data availability, integrity, security and usability for multiple end users and organisations and actively work to avoid data silos.
- **Semantic/Linked Data:** Data enrichment by linking to registered concepts in an ontology-based layer.
- **Standardization of Data Interfaces:** Wherever possible, international standards and de facto standards for data formats are used. This approach minimizes the need for conversion layers and maximizes interoperability.

If datasets are shared between project partners as part of the project, it is recommended that they be annotated according to the table (Table 2) below.

6.1 Data labelling

The data should be annotated to ensure full transparency and to increase the likelihood that the data is shared with the correct permissions. The annotation should look like this (Table 2):

Table 2: Data table to be completed for each dataset (data set information)

Data set name	NAME
Data set classification	Sensitive/Public
Data set references	SYNERGIES_XX Each data set will have a reference that will be generated by the combination of the name of the project and the reference number
Data set owner	Owner organisation(s) and contact person(s)
Organisations the data owner has provided authorisation for usage	The name(s) of organisations that the data has been shared with, and the intended usage of the data

Source	Data set source (specify reuse if applicable)
WP's	WPs in the SYNERGIES project.
Data set description	Each data set will have a full data description explaining the data provenance, origin and usefulness. Reference may be made to existing data that could be reused.
Data format	All the format that defines data.
Data size	Size of the data set.
Derived data	Data extracted from the created data set.
Data sharing	Explanation of the sharing policies related to the data set, including any associated terms and conditions (i.e., data generated outside of the project)
Reuse of existing data	If applicable
Archiving and preservation	The preservation guarantee and the data storage during and after the project (databases, institutional repositories, public repositories...)

The data should be annotated in a prominent position. For example, as with standard Microsoft or similar applications, this should be on the first or second page/slide. When sharing data, such as cloud storage, simulation platforms, etc., it is recommended that the annotations are communicated in an appropriate manner. Either in the system itself or by prior notification before access is granted.

6.2 Versioning

The versioning of the dataset, folder structure and file names should include the following information in the title: the creator or contributor, the creation date and the access conditions. This will make the data easier to find. Each structure should be organized as follows:

- DATE: YYYY-MM-DD (ISO8601)
- TIME: hh:mm:ss (ISO8601)
- TITLE: Data set title
- OWNER: Author using email address
- PARTNER: Partner short name
- WP-TASK: DoA Linked Task, e.g. WP3T2.2
- MAJOR: Major Version Number "XX."
- MINOR: Minor Version Number ".YY"
- DIST: DoA Distribution level

7 DATA STORAGE AND DATA ARCHIVING

To further enhance the platform’s capabilities, SYNERGIES incorporates robust data archiving and storage solutions. The platform’s data management strategy includes comprehensive data protection measures, metadata documentation, and support for data interoperability, in compliance with the FAIR principles. This approach not only facilitates efficient data retrieval and usage but also ensures the long-term preservation and accessibility of valuable datasets.

In the intermediate Data Management Plan, we will provide more detailed information on these data archiving and storage solutions, as who and where the data will be stored. This will include specific methodologies, technologies employed, and best practices for maintaining data integrity and security. By offering this in-depth insight, we aim to equip stakeholders with the knowledge needed to effectively manage and utilize the data within the SYNERGIES Platform.

8 DATA EXCHANGE AND DATA SHARING

The way in which data is exchanged and disseminated is of the most importance. The project brings together a wide range of partners with different internal processes and objectives, from commercial and technical companies to research organisations. It is essential that a common understanding of how data is shared, the conditions under which data is made public and the processes of agreement of such conditions is established and maintained. In doing so, a culture of trust can be established, which in turn will enhance the collaboration of the partners, and ultimately the project outcomes. Whilst the day-to-day interactions between partners and employing the appropriate level of due diligence is what builds such trust and fundamentally, data will be exchanged and shared in line with the requirements of the GA, CA and all applicable data protection legislation, this section will provide guidance and recommendations on best practice.

8.1 Data flow

It is expected that most of the data will either flow into or be generated within the technical and co-operation work packages. In all cases it is expected that all partners will handle data with ‘the same degree of care with regard to the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the Project as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care’ (CA, clause 10.5).

8.2 Data ownership

The data originator is the organisation that originally created the data. Unless otherwise and explicitly stated it should be assumed the data originator owns the data and has the authority and responsibility to define who that data can be shared with, for what purpose and its classification. The data originator should follow the best practice guidelines in this DMP and within their organisation when sharing data, including clear classification and labelling.

8.3 Data classification

The simplest and most effective way of ensuring data is handled with care is a simple classification system. The SYNERGIES project will have two levels of classification:

1. Sensitive or confidential
2. Public

Sensitive or confidential

Data classified as sensitive or confidential is limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement and Collaboration Agreement. In this instance the data originator should clearly label the data before sharing it. It is recommended this labelling is made bold and red.

Furthermore, it is recommended that the ‘Labelling’ guidelines of chapter 6.1 in Table 2 are followed to ensure the purpose for sharing the data is made clear to the recipient. It should not be assumed ‘Sensitive/ Confidential’ data can be shared with the whole consortia. It may be shared for the purpose of completing a work package or task. Any recipient of ‘Sensitive/ Confidential’ data should identify the data originator and gain their permission before sharing with other project partners or beyond the project. Data labelled as ‘Sensitive/Confidential’ should not be shared with other project partners or outside the

project without approval from the data originator. It should be noted that in certain circumstances data may be shared outside of the project and remain sensitive/confidential, for example to share with the Commission, or with Standardization Bodies. It is required that the data originator is always consulted, and that the labelling processes outlined in Table 2 be followed so the intended recipients and usages are followed.

NB: This text is only intended as guidance, the terms of the GA and CA will at all times take precedence.

Public

Public data refers to information that is freely available to the public. Public data is typically accessible without restrictions, although some datasets may require registration or have terms of use. Legal conditions may also apply, such as a creative commons copyright or an open-source license. It is recommended that any data in whatever format and classification (or without classification) is verified as approved for public dissemination with the data originator before being made public. For data that falls within GDPR, additional consideration may be needed. Please refer to the subsequent section of this DMP.

8.4 Interoperability

In order to support the exchange and reuse of data, standard data and metadata vocabularies, data standards formats (JSON-LD, RDF, XML) and methodologies will be employed by all partners. A detailed overview and list of the vocabulary used and the formats and methods employed will be provided in the next report when the project partners have agreed on a set of preferred formats. In the case of using proprietary formats, data adapters are available. Data adapters are essential tools available for utilizing existing data formats. These components are widely used in software development to facilitate the seamless transfer of data between a data source and a dataset. Acting as a bridge, data adapters enable the reading of data from a source. Furthermore, data interoperability will be managed in line with FAIR principles.

9 DATA ACCESS AND RESTRICTIONS

In the context of the SYNERGIES project, effective data management is crucial for the successful development, training, and validation of cooperative, connected, and automated mobility (CCAM) systems. This chapter outlines our approach to data access and restrictions, emphasizing the principles of open data, compliance with data protection laws, and ethical considerations. By fostering a transparent and collaborative environment, we aim to enhance the usability and impact of our research outcomes.

9.1 Protection principles

The SYNERGIES project is grounded in the belief that open access to research data is essential for innovation and collaboration. We adhere to key principles that govern our data management practices [1]:

- **Lawfulness and Fairness:** All data collection and processing activities will comply with applicable laws and regulations, ensuring that data subjects are treated fairly.
- **Transparency:** We commit to being transparent about how data is collected, used, and shared, providing clear information to stakeholders.
- **Purpose Limitation:** Data will only be collected for specified, legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner incompatible with those purposes.
- **Data Minimization:** We will collect only the data necessary for our objectives, reducing the risk of unnecessary exposure.
- **Accuracy:** Efforts will be made to ensure that data is accurate and kept up to date, with mechanisms in place for regular review.
- **Storage Limitation:** Data will be retained only as long as necessary for the purposes for which it was collected, after which it will be securely deleted.
- **Integrity and Confidentiality:** We will implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to protect data against unauthorized access, loss, or damage.
- **Accountability:** The project will maintain records of data processing activities and ensure compliance with these principles.

9.2 FAIR data principles

To further enhance data accessibility and usability, the SYNERGIES project embraces the FAIR data principles [2]:

- **Findable:** Data will be assigned unique identifiers and metadata to facilitate easy discovery.
- **Accessible:** We will ensure that data is available in a format that is easy to access and use, while respecting any necessary restrictions.
- **Interoperable:** Data will be structured in a way that allows it to be integrated with other datasets, promoting collaboration across projects.
- **Reusable:** Clear licensing and documentation will be provided to enable others to reuse the data effectively.

9.3 Compliance with data protection laws

The SYNERGIES project is committed to complying with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other relevant data protection laws., such as the UK data protection act or the Swiss federal act on data protection. This includes:

- **Personal Data Handling:** Any personal data collected will be processed lawfully, with explicit consent obtained where necessary. Data subjects will be informed of their rights regarding their data.
- **Data Protection Impact Assessments:** We will conduct assessments to identify and mitigate risks associated with data processing activities.

Partners which are established in a non-EU country undertake to comply with their obligations under the GA and to respect general principles (including fundamental rights, values and ethical principles, environmental and labour standards, rules on classified information, intellectual property rights, visibility of funding and protection of personal data).

9.4 Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations are integral to our data management strategy. We will ensure that:

- **Stakeholder Engagement:** All relevant stakeholders, including data subjects, will be engaged in discussions about data use and sharing.
- **Respect for Privacy:** We will prioritize the privacy of individuals and communities, ensuring that data collection methods are respectful and non-intrusive.
- **Transparency in Research:** We will communicate openly about our research objectives and methodologies, fostering trust among stakeholders.

10 DATA SECURITY

Data security is primordial for the SYNERGIES Project, ensuring the protection of sensitive information and maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of data throughout its lifecycle. In order to maintain data security, the following principles will be taken into account:

- **Confidentiality:** sensitive information will only be accessible to those authorized to access the data
- **Integrity:** the data stored needs to maintain its consistency over its lifecycle.
- **Availability:** data needs to be accessible and available to users when they need it.
- **Accountability:** the data will be traceable, its origin will be known and will be included in the data inventory that will be provided in the intermediate DPM.
- **Transparency:** data handling practices will be open and clear.
- **Data minimization:** only the data needed specifically for the purposes of the project will be gathered.
- **Resilience:** the data storage systems will be resistant to disruption, cyber-attacks and system failures. The intermediate version will provide the common practices by the data hosts.

Adherence to these security principles will ensure that the lifecycle of the data is properly followed. In the intermediate version of this DMP, a more thorough and comprehensive information will be provided with regards to the security measures taken by each of the organizations that host data.

11 DATA PUBLISHING AND LICENSING

11.1 Publishing

This process is thoroughly described in D10.1 (Dissemination and Communication Plan), which has already been submitted. To avoid duplication and potential ambiguity, it is not reiterated here. The information can be found in D10.1 Annex A.

11.2 Licensing

The terms under which data is licensed are agreed at the time of licensing but are always in accordance with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement.

12 COSTS

The costs of managing data in line with FAIR principles, including costs relating to archiving and long-term storage have been considered and included in the proposal by each partner. Financial management for the project shall be in line with the terms of the GA and CA and in as much as adherence to the terms of the GA and CA allows, partners shall bear the costs associated with making the data owned by the partner findable, accessible, and re-useable.

13 CONCLUSIONS

The document provides guidelines and best practices for data management within the SYNERGIES project, ensuring its successful implementation. It is based on the Consortium Agreement (CA) and the Grant Agreement (GA). The CA contains the data management provisions agreed between the project partners. The GA contains the data management provisions agreed with the European Commission. These agreements are supplemented in the DMP with project-level guidelines for processes and procedures to ensure effective data management.

Responsibility for the implementation of the DMP lies with all project members according to their roles and responsibilities. The Project Coordinator, Working Group Leaders and Task Leaders will ensure compliance with the DMP under the guidance and supervision of the Data Protection Officer.

Please note that the DMP in no way replaces the legal documents of the project and their application. In case of doubt, the legally binding documents take precedence.

The objective of this document is to outline the general data management plan for the project and the correct and appropriate handling of personal data that needs to be protected or that requires special treatment from an ethical point of view. When collecting, processing or using personal data by a project member, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other legal requirements must first be taken into account. These requirements are explained in the DMP.

In addition, the FAIR Principles are highlighted in the DMP as an important guideline to ensure findability, accessibility, interoperability and reproducibility of data. The principles are summarized in the DMP, together with an explanation of the commitment to follow these principles. The SYNERGIES project intends to follow the FAIR principles wherever possible, taking into account commercial and practical constraints.

The way in which the data is managed and disseminated is critical to the success of the project. The project unites a variety of partners with different internal processes and objectives from different sectors such as business, technology and research. It is essential to establish and maintain a common understanding of how data will be handled, the conditions under which data will be published and the procedures for agreeing these conditions. In this way, a culture of trust can be built that improves collaboration between partners and, ultimately, project outcomes. The DMP provides guidelines and recommendations for good practice that can be considered by partners in their daily interactions and in the appropriate application of due diligence.

As soon as the project partners recognize the relevance of the data and results for the public, they will evaluate the possibilities of publication in accordance with the guidelines of this DMP and the requirements of the CA and GA. The DMP contains best practices and procedures for the provision of data within the project and for the archiving and availability of these data beyond the project period.

The SYNERGIES project recognizes that effective data access and management are vital for achieving its objectives. By adhering to the principles of open data, ensuring compliance with data protection laws, and prioritizing ethical considerations, we aim to create a robust framework that supports innovation and collaboration in the field of CCAM systems.

This document provides initial guidance that explains project implementation in a simple and practical way, supports compliance with the underlying legal obligations and promotes the application of best data management practices.

As the project progresses, the DMP will be continuously updated to enable efficient integration, creation and management of FAIR data.

14 REFERENCES

- [1] European Data Protection Board (EDPB). (2021). "Guidelines on Examples regarding Data Protection by Design and by Default." Available at: <https://edpb.europa.eu>
- [2] Wilkinson, M. D., et al. (2016). "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship." *Scientific Data*, 3(160018). DOI:10.1038/sdata.2016.18.
- [3] SYNERGIES Consortium (2024). Grant Agreement.
- [4] SYNERGIES Consortium (2024). Consortium Agreement.
- [5] OECD. (2021). "Recommendation of the Council concerning Access to Research Data from Public Funding." DOI:10.1787/9789264252875-en.
- [6] International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2019). "ISO 19115-1: Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals." Available at: <https://www.iso.org>.
- [7] Smith, J., & Dodoiu, T. (2023). *D1.3: Data Management Plan*. SUNRISE. Available at: <https://ccam-sunrise-project.eu/deliverable/d1-3-data-management-plan/>.

A. QUESTIONNAIRE

Data Description

- What is the origin/provenance of the data (generated/ re-used)?
- What types and formats of data will the project generate/re-use?
- Are you using a file format that is standard in your field? If not, how will you document the alternative you are using?
- What existing data do you expect to use within the project (re-use)?
- What methodologies or software for data collection or production are you going to use?

Data Management

- What data management standards do you expect/require for the project?
- What tools or software are required to manage the data?

Data Storage

- Where and how is the data stored?
- What is the expected volume of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- Who decides and how, what data to keep and for how long?
- Will the data be identified by a persistent identifier? If so, how (e.g. Digital Object Identifiers)?
- What metadata will be created?
- What general standards will be followed? If metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Outline the approach to search keywords. Will keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility of discovery and subsequent re-use?
- Will metadata be provided in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?
- Will documentation or references to any software required to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?

Data Archiving

- How will long term preservation be ensured?
- Until when will data be available?

Data Exchange and Sharing

- What are the guiding principles for data exchange internally and externally?
- What is the expected data flow in the project?
- Who owns the data and has responsibility to define who data may be shared with?
- Under what conditions will data be made public?
- What are the processes for agreeing the conditions under which data will be made public?
- How will data that is intended to be shared externally be classified and labelled?

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to enable data exchange and re-use?
- Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? If so, which ones?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?
- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable.
- Specify when the data will be made available for re-use.
- If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed.

Data Access and Restrictions

- Will the data used in the project be open data?
- If data of the project is open, what is the way in which it would be shared?
- If the data of the project is not open data who will be able to access it (all partners, only ones that provided the data, etc.)?
- If the data of the project is not open to public, for how long will the partners have rights to access it?
- Will every request for sharing the data be individually assessed?
- Will the data, after the duration of the project, become publicly available?
- Would the partners be able to use the data after the project is completed?
- Will the data from other partners be available even after the project is concluded?
- After the project conclusion, will the partners be obliged to destroy the data?
- How is the destruction of the data checked and enforced?
- What are the regulations and enforcements for data deletion, and will there be governing body that checks if the deed is done?
- How will we do the data access? How will be the governing party to decide the data access?
- How is the data provided by the partners weighed since not all partners will provide same amount of data?
- Who is dedicated and ensure that restrictions are met?
- On which level data sharing will be done between partners?
- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

- If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- What tools or software are required to read or view the data?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?
- How long will the data remain available and findable?
- Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited.

Data Security

- Where is data stored?
- What security measures are there?
- Is there a back-up policy? If so, how it work?
- Will there be any paper-based documentation stored? How will it be stored?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions
- What are the guidelines for the secure storage and transfer of sensitive data?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Data Publishing and Licensing

- How and when will the data be published and/or licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?
- What are the guiding principles and agreed processes regarding public dissemination?
- To whom might your data be useful ("data utility") outside your project?
- Will the metadata be provided with a CC0 licence for the public domain in accordance with the grant agreement?
- Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Costs

- What are the costs for making data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-useable in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

- Is there budget allocation for storage?
- Describe the costs for long-term archiving and are they available?
- How will these costs be met?
- Are there any other costs? If so, what costs and how much?

B. ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Term	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
CSV	Comma-separated values
CCAM	Cooperative, connected and automated mobility
DM	Dissemination Manager
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DoA	Description of the Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPRM	Intellectual property rights Manager
IPR	Intellectual property rights
IP	Intellectual property
IEM	Innovation and Exploitation Manager
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KB	Kilobyte
LCM	Liaison and Collaboration Manager
MB	Megabyte
ODD	Operational Domain Design
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
R&D	Research and development
RDF	Resource Description Framework
TB	Terabyte
UC	Use case
WP	Work Package